

PHYSICAL AND MENTAL DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN THROUGH ACTIVITY GAMES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

This article discusses the importance of mobile games in child development and the role of mobile games in educating, developing and educating the individual, preparing children for social life.

Key words: Maria Montessori, creative, preschool education, preschool education, movement games, physical development

INTRODUCTION

"A child can teach himself, only you and your limitations block his way."

Maria Montessori, the teacher of children of the world, did not write these words for nothing. The surrounding people and environment are the biggest factor in the child's development.

The future of any society depends in every way on the young people who are sane, broad-minded, thirst for knowledge, creative thinkers and have highly developed intellectual potential. Only a perfectly sane generation will be able to take actions that are important to the Motherland and the country as a whole, and determine the historical destiny of its people. From this point of view, the role of the education given to him in the development of every person is incomparable. Today's processes of globalization, science and technology development, young people who want to have an innovative society, work on many new ideas and approach with creativity is considered the need of the hour. They are faced with vital requirements such as quick decision-making, innovative thinking, intelligent software, and adherence to universal values. The first foundation of education is definitely laid in the first stage of the educational process in the organization of preschool education.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Humanization of preschool education is the basis of the process of its renewal. More and more scientists and practicing specialists come to the conclusion that the system of physical education of preschool children should have a complex, human effect on the individual, and should ensure the realization of the right of every child to regular and as full physical development as possible. At the moment, the environment surrounding children is changing. Simple, simple games were replaced by computer games. The graphics and colors of the games captivate children. Today's era, which is considered the age of technology, has a negative effect on children's healthy and well-rounded growth. Mental and aesthetic development of the child is becoming a priority. Without denying their importance, it should be said that the child's time for active games, walks, and communication with peers is getting less and less.

Game and other types of children's activities, imbalance between different types of games (active and sitting, separate and joint) have a negative impact on the health of

preschool children and the level of development of motor skills. Finding new ways to solve the problems of physical development of preschool children, firstly, with the need to resolve the indicated conflicts, and secondly, with the need to study the laws, methodological and methodological conditions of improving the development process of physical fitness of the growing young generation. inextricably linked. A serious feature of early infancy is the interrelationship and interdependence of the child's health and physical development. Accordingly, it is necessary to make preschool children physically healthy, develop the child's range of motion, and form life skills such as being agile, strong, and brave. Therefore, the purpose of conducting work on this topic is to determine the theoretical foundations and methodical ways of developing the technology of children's movement activity in preschool education organizations based on the use of movement games as a means of physical education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Every action game has a useful purpose. Only if the growing young generation develops in a healthy way, it will reach the level of a perfect human being both mentally and spiritually. For this reason, all active games should become an integral part of a child's life. The role of active games in child education and development is incomparable. First of all, these games are not played just for fun. Each game has its own content, purpose and mission. A child is born, and his whole life is connected with action. It is the duty of parents to teach and apply these actions correctly. The earlier you start working with a child, the more successful things will be in the future.

As long as we form active games in the child's mind from a young age, these games will serve to ensure the child's health. And we should adapt these games to the child's age. After all, it is impossible to teach a 4-5-year-old child and a 1-2-year-old baby in the same way. It is necessary to approach taking into account the child's age and psychology. As we know, imitation is more common in preschool children's games. In this way, the child is interested in the environment. Tevarak starts looking around for more interesting things to add to his game. As children observe and imitate the life of animals, in a sense, the child learns to think, understand, and overcome difficulties. As the child spends his life interestingly and meaningfully, his interest in life increases consciously. At the same time, physical activity also begins to improve. As we all know, the body of a young child is developing gradually. Active games are also important for the child's training, proper development of bones and height.

For example, a child does not forget a new game after playing it for a day, but adds something interesting to it every day. A game that interests a child is connected with movement and a child's life. So, active games are considered an important factor in the mental and physical development of a young child. The child, who has been playing various interesting games since his youth, stands out from his peers at school age by his cheerfulness and mobility. Children of junior school age get to know national games while playing national action games. National action games form our national values in children. At the same time, it ensures the healthy development of the child. A number of examples of national action games can be given ("White poplar or blue poplar?", "Cockfight", "Happak", etc.). Each game has its own goal. The game "Cockfight" develops responsibility and leadership skills in children. Thus, as the child grows up, the games become more complicated. As a result, the child's physical qualities begin to increase.

According to Aristotle's book "Khitoba", "young men with excellent physical abilities, healthy, tall, are agile in sports competitions, and youth from this are the wealth of any country." The growth of such wealth depends on our efforts and research. In fact, making a child interested in active games increases his passion for sports. This passion will surely help the child to become a famous athlete in the future and to introduce his country to the whole world.

CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the physiological mechanisms that determine various forms of interdependence of strength, speed and endurance in childhood are also diverse. Conditional-reflective factors are important. Certain forms of programming of the work of muscles and vegetative organs occur in the central nervous system for actions that develop strength, speed or endurance in a certain direction during training. Movement games ensure the implementation of the task of complex development of movement skills as much as possible, because their content is focused on the formation and replacement of movement programs.

Older preschoolers are able to evaluate their own efforts and capabilities as they compete in strength (hand pull), speed (sprint, shuttle run) and other qualities. In addition to physical development, active games help children develop willpower, courage, perseverance, endurance, and courage. Children usually try to satisfy their great need for movement through games. For children, play means, first of all, activity, movement. During active games, children's movements improve, initiative and independence, confidence and perseverance develop. They learn to coordinate their actions and even follow some rules (at first, of course, in a simple form).

Every movement makes the child's body come alive. Carrying out these actions in the form of various games ensures the health of the child. If the fun games that preschool children have been playing since they were young are the foundation for action games, national action games will be the pillar of this foundation. The content of the columns is action games, the essence is sports action games. The main goal and task of these games is to help the growing young generation to grow up to be a mentally, mentally, spiritually and physically mature person.

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